

MODERN-INNOVATIVE PRINCIPLES OF IMPROVING SCHOOL, FAMILY AND NEIGHBORHOOD COOPERATION IN PROVIDING ENVIRONMENTAL AND LEGAL EDUCATION TO SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract. *The purpose of providing ecological legal knowledge is to apply this knowledge in life. Therefore, the next step in providing environmental legal education is teaching to use this knowledge in practice, that is, the process of environmental education.*

Keywords: *"brainstorming", "brainstorming", "networks" method, "siquain", "debate", "role play", "working in small groups", "snowball", "zigzag", "i have the last word"*

In order to properly solve environmental problems in any society, a person should be well aware of the relationship between himself and nature and their laws, as well as systematically positively solve pedagogical, economic, philosophical, legal and other directions.

As Islam Karimov, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, said, "...at the turn of the century, the whole of humanity, the population of our country, faced a great ecological danger. Not realizing this, sitting idly by is tantamount to condemning oneself to death. "Unfortunately, many still treat this problem carelessly and irresponsibly."

Humanity was created so that, as a product of nature, it lives in harmony with it. However, over the centuries, as a result of the growing influence of the concepts of ecological and legal education surrounding humanity, and the irrational use of natural resources, a lot of damage has been caused to the environment. As a result, changes in nature and environmental ecology are bringing unprecedented disasters to mankind. Natural and man-made events in environmental ecology, including strong winds, typhoons, climate changes, earthquakes, floods, and landslides, are taking the lives of many people and causing great damage to the economy of countries. due to the fact that it has not been put, we hesitate in the factors that invite us to draw conclusions about the precautionary approach to environmental ecology, due to the fact that we do not know how to react to the emergency environmental events. They need to wake people up.

For this purpose, the formation of concepts of cooperation of school, family and neighborhood in environmental legal education of students and the issue of careful attitude to the environment as an integral part of human life have been deeply embedded in the way of life of our people since time immemorial. Its necessity is highlighted in epics, fairy tales, proverbs, parables, narrations and wisdom, which are examples of folk art. Life-long traditions, customs and values passed down from centuries to centuries, from ancestors to generations, reflect the nation's life philosophy and lifestyle with all its being. No matter what time, no matter what the circumstances, our ancestors worried about their ancestors becoming perfect people in all respects. Because only children who are physically and mentally healthy, spiritually high, have deep knowledge and a mature profession, and morally pure children are the true successors of the generation, the owners

of the country, the wealth of the nation, and they are considered to be the managers and providers of the state.

The cooperation of school, family and neighborhood in providing students with ecological and legal education requires the formation and development of concepts:

- Feeling that nature is a place where humanity lives, a source of life, a field of activity, a center of education;
- knowledge of environmental problems caused by human activity;
- to have information about environmental problems in the territory of the republic, their causes, consequences, measures to improve acute environmental situations;
- to know and follow the legislation on environmental protection;
- development of feelings of kindness towards nature, ecological values, ecological standards;
- formation of environmental culture and faith in students' outlook;
- understanding and following natural, national, universal values.

In accordance with these ideas, the formation and development of the concepts of school, family and community cooperation in ecological and legal education of students is an important socio-pedagogical necessity. It is necessary for all our students to know these ideas.

Also, ecological legal education and training issues are not paid much attention in textbooks of ecological law. Therefore, in our opinion, it is appropriate to recognize "Ecological legal education and training" as a separate institution, to be studied and to show a number of sub-institutes in environmental law.

Scientific principle of ecological legal education that each piece of knowledge imparted is said to be explained based on knowledge that has been experienced several times before and is well known to the students.

In this principle, it is necessary to explain and analyze the logic and history of the new knowledge along with its scientific justification. The principle of taking into account the capabilities and age characteristics of learners. According to the sciences of physiology and psychology, a person is never born with the same talent, his ability to receive, understand and retain knowledge is different.

These abilities are different for everyone, they change with age and can be improved through special exercises. Based on these thoughts, before teaching, every teacher must know the processes taking place in the psyche of students. In addition, he must be aware of the ability of each child to receive and retain knowledge, the type and amount of knowledge he has accumulated so far. Only then will his pedagogical influence on students be effective.

The principle of demonstrability in environmental legal education and training. When this principle is followed, the organs of vision are involved as well as the organs of hearing of the person. According to the research of world scientists, the level of memory retention of the knowledge acquired through the senses is as follows: 15-20% of the knowledge acquired through the auditory organs is remembered, while 80-85% of the knowledge acquired through the sight is remembered. Therefore, the principle of demonstrability is one of the main principles of the educational process. The saying of our people that "it is better to see once than to hear a hundred times" confirms this. But if demonstrativeness has a good effect, if its norm is violated, that is, if there are too many exhibition materials, the attention of learners will be spread, and their thoughts will be distracted from the main content of the lesson.

The principle of connecting environmental legal education with life, it is said to connect education with life and production practices. It is one of the main and leading rules of didactics and is derived from the spiritual foundations of knowledge activity. This principle is inextricably linked with other principles of education, including the principle of scientificity. It is aimed at realizing that the theoretical knowledge obtained during the study was discovered due to practical needs.

The principle of unity of practice with environmental legal education - it is carried out in the course of teaching, depending on the content and specific characteristics of the subject. This unity constitutes a whole educational process with mental phenomena such as thorough assimilation of knowledge and ability to use it in practice, as well as its consolidation.

The principle of awareness and activism in environmental legal education. In order for students to be able to use the knowledge they are getting in life, it is necessary to turn the teaching process into active thinking. In this case, teaching should be organized in such a way that students acquire knowledge by consciously and actively participating in classes. Then students' ecological legal awareness will grow, creative initiative and independence in learning activities will be formed.

Systematic and consistent principle of environmental legal education. Strict consistency must be observed in education, so that the environmental knowledge learned today builds on what was learned yesterday, strengthens them, and prepares the ground for what will be learned tomorrow. The principle of systematic and consistency ensures the rule of didactics from general to specific and from specific to general in the teaching process, as well as the inextricable connection of academic subjects with each other.

The principle of unity of environmental education and upbringing - It requires giving people environmental knowledge and teaching them to use this knowledge in life, as well as the overall development of students. In the whole process of education and upbringing, it is manifested in mutual knowledge and teaching to act on the basis of this knowledge, knowledge of the laws in objective existence and formation of its practical relationship. Environmental education takes the lead in this process. Because without providing ecological legal knowledge, a person cannot be taught to apply this knowledge to life.

On the basis of the above, it should be said that it is important to rely on the principle of unity of education in the implementation of environmental legal education for students. In our opinion, these include:

- educating students of environmental and legal education;

Adherence and implementation of the above-mentioned principles of ecological-legal education creates a special direction of relations of students' relationship with nature, the natural environment, and:

- first of all, that students see themselves as "an integral part and whole piece" of nature;

- secondly, students perceive nature as a factor and value that determines the main ecological and legal aspects of life;

- thirdly, if all types of human relations with nature are carried out only on the basis of mutual ecological and legal interest, harmony between nature and man is manifested, and if this harmony is disturbed, an ecological disaster may occur. The occurrence of ecological disasters depends on the ecological-legal knowledge and ecological-legal culture of the society, every person living in it, including students. As an example, the consequences of the Arol disaster, the

negative effects of the Regar Aluminum plant in Tajikistan can be shown. That is why it is possible to evaluate the environmental and legal education of young people in three ways: positive, negative and indifferent.

Therefore, the correct conduct and formation of environmental-legal education and training for students based on the above principles, as well as widening their practical activities in this direction, will help raise environmental-legal education to a higher level.

Today, the implementation of advanced pedagogic and new information technologies in conducting ecological and legal education not only increases the effectiveness of training sessions, but also takes an important role in educating an independent and logically thinking, all-round highly moral person by applying the achievements of science in practice.

Although the theory of pedagogical technology has been based since the second half of the last century, there are different approaches to the concept of "pedagogical technology". In particular, pedagogue scientist V.P.Bespalko defines pedagogical technology as "the project of a specific pedagogical system applied in practice" and focuses on the preliminary design of the educational and pedagogical process.

Pedagogical technology is the process by which the teacher has a new effect on students in a specific situation with the help of teaching tools. In the new pedagogical technology, it is necessary to implement the teaching system traditionally implemented in higher educational institutions on a scientific basis. The knowledge, skills, creative activity formed in the students during the experience is the product of the pedagogical process.

Because in this, students' ability to learn, remember, understand, master, prove, analyze, compare, draw conclusions, apply to life, connect, process information creatively, and acquire new knowledge will be perfected. In the structure of the educational process, special importance is given to the general purpose and content of education, educational goals, teaching and learning, evaluation, etc. For this, a group of leading Methodist pedagogues develops methodical materials based on the principle of pedagogical technology. If such materials are available, the teacher's role is mainly to organize and give advice.

In general, the general structure of designing educational activities in the pedagogical technology method is as follows: the name of the subject includes information sources, equipment, textbooks, training manuals, teachers, audio-visual tools, computerized educational materials, modern automated computer systems, multimedia, etc.

In the process of conducting ecological and legal education, trainings using modern technologies are aimed at students to find the acquired knowledge by themselves, study and analyze it independently, and even draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual and the team, at the same time, he performs the task of management and orientation. In such an educational process, the student becomes the main figure.

The teacher usually sets the goal of teaching the student to understand, master and apply the content of the educational material, and in practice there are many options for implementing and conducting the educational process.

In connection with the development of the educational process, it is appropriate to use cooperative pedagogy, game technologies, problem-based learning, programmed learning, and group technologies in designing the educational process.

Pedagogical technologies based on the activation and acceleration of student activity in the process of conducting ecological-legal education. Problem-based learning, games, basic signal synopsis technologies, and more.

Pedagogical technologies based on didactic improvement and redevelopment of educational material. These technologies are based on principles such as the didactic system of taught knowledge having a deep content, approaching ecological and legal knowledge from a systematic point of view, and teaching students the most appropriate ways of acquiring knowledge.

Pedagogical technologies based on effective management and organization of the educational process. These technologies include stratified, individualized, programmed educational technologies; includes team method of education, group, computer educational technologies. Pedagogical technologies adapted to nature. These include the student's natural opportunities, natural opportunities for organizing the ecological educational process, and other pedagogical technologies based on the full use of opportunities in accordance with nature.

Developmental educational technologies. These include technologies for developing the positive qualities of the student's personality, knowledge in certain areas, creative abilities.

Today, the interest in using interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day in providing environmental and legal education to students. One of the reasons for this is that until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, and the use of modern technologies teaches them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, to study independently and to think, analyze, and even draw final conclusions by themselves. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for personal development, formation, learning and upbringing, and at the same time performs the function of management and guidance. Today in education "Brainstorming", "Thinking of ideas", "Networks" method, "Sinquain", "Discussion", "Role-playing", "Working in small groups", "Snowball", "Zigzag", "Last modern technologies such as "I say the word" are used.

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